

D2O_ModelCreation

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0.0.1 Effect of surfactants on the thermoresponse of PNIPAM investigated in the brush geometry

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For additional details regarding the use of refnx, see the [paper](#) or [read the docs](#).

For additional details regarding the use of the freeform model, or for details regarding the usefulness of MCMC for NR analysis, see the [paper](#)

For additional details regarding MCMC (implimented via emcee), see the [paper](#) or [read the docs](#)

For additional details regarding PT-MCMC (implimented via ptmcee), see the [paper](#) or [read the docs](#)

To follow this example, run the notebooks in the following order 1. D2O_ModelCreation.ipynb 2. CM_ModelCreation.ipynb 3. MCMC.ipynb

```
[1]: %matplotlib inline
```

```
[2]: import pickle
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from scipy.stats import norm, truncnorm
import copy

from refnx.reflect import SLD, Slab, ReflectModel, MixedReflectModel
from refnx.dataset import ReflectDataset as RD
from refnx.analysis import Objective, CurveFitter, PDF, Parameter, □
    ↪process_chain, load_chain

import sys
sys.path.append('./Code')

from FreeformVFP import FreeformVFP
import plottools
from GenericBrushObjective import make_brush_objective
```

```

def unpack_values (values):
    std_norm_bounds = (-1.96,1.96) #https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/1.96
    return values[1], (values[0], values[2]), truncnorm(*std_norm_bounds,
    ↪loc=values[1], scale=(values[2]-values[0])/(2*1.96))

def set_param(params, pname, value):
    for p in params.flattened():
        if p.name == pname:
            if p.vary:
                p.value = p.bounds.valid(value)
                break

def save_diffev_results(fitter, save_dir):
    np.savetxt(f'{save_dir}/diffev_bestparams_{fitter.objective.name}',
    ↪fitter.objective.varying_parameters())
    pickle.dump(fitter.objective, open(f'{save_dir}/diffev_bestobj_{fitter.
    ↪objective.name}.pkl', 'wb'))
    return np.round(fitter.objective.logpost(),2), fitter.objective.
    ↪varying_parameters()

def print_fitqual(objectives):
    for idx, objective in enumerate(objectives):
        red_chisqr = objective.chisqr()/len(objective.data.x)
        print (f"{idx}: {objective.name}, {np.round(objective.logpost())}, {np.
    ↪round(red_chisqr,2)}")

```

```

[3]: # Version numbers allow you to repeat the analysis on your computer and obtain
    ↪identical results.
import refnx, scipy
refnx.__version__, np.version.version, scipy.version.version

```

```

[3]: ('0.1.16', '1.22.3', '1.7.3')

```

Using relevant values with their 95% confidence interval from PTMCMC sampling of the dry dataset + 40°C data in both D2O and NIPAM-CM water. This should have the best shot at characterizing the silica layer and dry polymer thickness.

```

[4]: prior_values = pd.read_csv('W10_SiO2 layer parameters.csv', index_col=0,
    ↪header=0,
                                names=['silica thick', 'silica SLD', 'silica-SiO2
    ↪rough', 'silica vfsolv', 'PNIPAM thick',
                                'PNIPAM SLD', 'PNIPAM vfsolv', 'PNIPAM
    ↪volume'])

polymer_ads_amt, polymer_ads_amt_bounds, polymer_ads_amt_dist =
    ↪unpack_values(prior_values['PNIPAM volume'])

```

```

sio2_thickness, sio2_thickness_bounds, sio2_thickness_dist      =␣
↳unpack_values(prior_values['silica thick'])
sio2_sld, sio2_sld_bounds, sio2_sld_dist                       =␣
↳unpack_values(prior_values['silica SLD'])
sio2_vfsolv, sio2_vfsolv_bounds, sio2_vfsolv_dist             =␣
↳unpack_values(prior_values['silica vfsolv'])
si_sio2_roughness, si_sio2_roughness_bounds, si_sio2_roughness_dist =␣
↳unpack_values(prior_values['silica-SiO2 rough'])

sio2_poly_rough = 1

```

[5]: prior_values

```

[5]:      silica thick  silica SLD  silica-SiO2 rough  silica vfsolv  \
q1      16.578260    3.293231      10.844933      0.076289
q2      18.559324    3.455169      12.826823      0.091450
q3      20.867145    3.616602      14.443033      0.107877
stdev   1.094103    0.082492      0.917883      0.008058

      PNIPAM thick  PNIPAM SLD  PNIPAM vfsolv  PNIPAM volume
q1      125.240686   0.575200      0.097191      110.527870
q2      125.762557   0.589260      0.110819      111.840543
q3      126.331105   0.606567      0.121890      113.472781
stdev   0.278168    0.008002      0.006301      0.751253

```

Now we construct the substrate layer (common between datasets)

```

[6]: si      = SLD(2.07, 'si')
sio2     = SLD(sio2_sld, 'sio2')
polymer  = SLD(0.8, 'PNIPAM')
polymer.real.setp(vary=True, bounds=(0.73, 1.3))

# Silicon
si_l     = si(0, 0)

# Silica
sio2_l   = sio2(sio2_thickness, si_sio2_roughness)
sio2_l.thick.setp (vary=True, bounds=sio2_thickness_dist)
sio2_l.sld.real.setp (vary=True, bounds=sio2_sld_dist)
sio2_l.vfsolv.setp (vary=True, value=sio2_vfsolv, bounds=sio2_vfsolv_dist)
sio2_l.rough.setp (vary=True, value=si_sio2_roughness,
↳bounds=si_sio2_roughness_dist)

bs = si_l | sio2_l

```

List what data you want to analyse. For simplicity, only a subset is selected by default

```
[7]: # fit_names = ["W10 lowdSDS-d2o 25C", "W10 lowdSDS-d2o 32C", "W10 lowdSDS-d2o
↳40C",
#           "W10 highdSDS-d2o 25C", "W10 highdSDS-d2o 32C", "W10
↳highdSDS-d2o 40C",
#           "W10 lowdC12E5-d2o 25C", "W10 lowdC12E5-d2o 32C", "W10
↳lowdC12E5-d2o 40C",
#           "W10 highdC12E5-d2o 25C", "W10 highdC12E5-d2o 32C", "W10
↳highdC12E5-d2o 40C",]

fit_names = ["W10 highdSDS-d2o 40C", "W10 highdC12E5-d2o 40C"]
```

For neatness, you could set the save directory to a subfolder

```
[8]: save_dir = './'
file_prepend = 'diffev_bestobj_'
data_dir = 'Data/'
```

Create datasets, optionally reloading from past results (useful if updating a current best fit with new bounds)

```
[9]: reload_values = True
objectives = []

for fit_name in fit_names:

    temp_objective = make_brush_objective(data_name=f'{data_dir}{fit_name}.
↳dat', base_structure=bs,
                                           polymer_sld=copy.deepcopy(polymer),
↳adsorbed_amount=polymer_ads_amt,
adsorbed_amount_bounds=polymer_ads_amt_dist,
                                           base_poly_rough=sio2_poly_rough,
↳name=fit_name,
                                           knot_num=5, enforce_mono='partial')
↳#was 4 by default

    if reload_values:
        try:
            saved_objective = pickle.
↳load(open(f'{save_dir}{file_prepend}{fit_name}.pkl', 'rb'))
#           saved_objective = pickle.load(open(f'{save_dir}/
↳diffev_bestobj_{fit_name}.pkl', 'rb'))
            for param in saved_objective.parameters.flattened():
                set_param(temp_objective.parameters, param.name, param.value)
            print(f'reloaded previous fit for {fit_name}.')
        except FileNotFoundError:
```

```

        print (f"no saved fit found for {fit_name}, using default starting_
        ↪values.")

```

```

objectives.append(temp_objective)

```

no saved fit found for W10 highdSDS-d2o 40C, using default starting values.
no saved fit found for W10 highdC12E5-d2o 40C, using default starting values.

Ensure that parameter bounds are valid (once again, useful if the old best fit has been updated with new bounds)

```

[10]: for idx, objective in enumerate(objectives):
        for param in objective.varying_parameters():
            param.value = param.bounds.valid(param.value)

```

1 Pre-optimisation Introspection

Plot objectives against data before optimisation.

Also check $\log(\text{prob})$ and χ^2 values before optimisation.

```

[11]: fig, ax = plottools.graph_plot(objective=objectives, vf_plot=True,
        ↪ystyle='rq4', xstyle='log', offset=0.01,
        color=plt.cm.plasma, orientation='h')

print_fitqual(objectives)

```

0: W10 highdSDS-d2o 40C, -18017.0, 323.11

1: W10 highdC12E5-d2o 40C, -26514.0, 465.85

2 Perform an optimisation with differential evolution

Useful for checking the model bounds are set correctly etc.

nits is the number of iterations per objective (will run DE nits times)

```

[12]: nits = 3

for objective in objectives:
    print('\n\n')
    fitter = CurveFitter(objective, ntemps=3, nwalkers=200)
    print('fitting: %s'%fitter.objective.name)

    best_lnprob, best_pvecs = save_diffev_results(fitter, save_direc=save_direc)

    try:
        print('starting least squares fit from initial position...')
        fitter.fit('least_squares')
        best_lnprob, best_pvecs = save_diffev_results(fitter,
↪save_direc=save_direc)
        print (f'Least Squares lnprob (from initial position): {best_lnprob}')
    except ValueError:
        print ('Initial position infesible, starting with differential
↪evolution.')

    for i in range(nits):
        print()
        print(f'Starting fit {i+1}, best prob: {best_lnprob}')

        fitter.fit('differential_evolution')
        fitter.fit('least_squares')
        red_chisqr = np.round(fitter.objective.chisqr()/len(fitter.objective.
↪data.x),2)

        print (f'Finished fit with final logpost: {fitter.objective.logpost()},
↪{red_chisqr}')

        if fitter.objective.logpost() > best_lnprob: # Fit is better than
↪previous
            best_lnprob, best_pvecs = save_diffev_results(fitter,
↪save_direc=save_direc)
            print (f'Best logpost now: {best_lnprob}, {red_chisqr}')
        else: # Fit is worse than previous
            print (f'Discarding most recent fit results. Best logpost still:
↪{best_lnprob}')
            fitter.objective.setp(best_pvecs)

    if red_chisqr < 1.5: # Fit is so good we can just quit now.
        print ('Terminating fit as reduced chisqr < 1.5.')
        break

```

fitting: W10 highdSDS-d2o 40C
starting least squares fit from initial position...
Least Squares lnprob (from initial position): 517.02

Starting fit 1, best prob: 517.02

Oit [00:00, ?it/s]/Volumes/GoogleDrive/My Drive/PhD/07 Papers/Surfactants/Paper
1 code repo/./Code/FreeformVFP.py:296: RuntimeWarning: extent > 3000, performing
refl. calc on first 3000A.

warnings.warn('extent > %d, performing refl. calc on first %dA.' %
165it [01:37, 1.70it/s]

Finished fit with final logpost: 1026.8074377965015, 2.92

Best logpost now: 1026.81, 2.92

Starting fit 2, best prob: 1026.81

260it [02:33, 1.69it/s]

Finished fit with final logpost: 1022.4059412688696, 3.01

Discarding most recent fit results. Best logpost still: 1026.81

Starting fit 3, best prob: 1026.81

210it [02:07, 1.65it/s]

Finished fit with final logpost: 1031.467887271575, 2.83

Best logpost now: 1031.47, 2.83

fitting: W10 highdC12E5-d2o 40C
starting least squares fit from initial position...
Least Squares lnprob (from initial position): 919.53

Starting fit 1, best prob: 919.53

306it [02:55, 1.74it/s]

Finished fit with final logpost: 1053.968629904329, 2.4

Best logpost now: 1053.97, 2.4

Starting fit 2, best prob: 1053.97

210it [02:01, 1.73it/s]

Finished fit with final logpost: 1045.059532619446, 2.58

Discarding most recent fit results. Best logpost still: 1053.97

Starting fit 3, best prob: 1053.97

684it [06:26, 1.77it/s]

Finished fit with final logpost: 1031.8552983069771, 2.83
Discarding most recent fit results. Best logpost still: 1053.97

3 Inspection after optimisation

```
[13]: fig, ax = plottools.graph_plot(objective=objectives, vf_plot=True,
    ↳ ystyle='rq4', xstyle='log', offset=0.01,
    color=plt.cm.plasma, orientation='h')

print_fitqual(objectives)
```

0: W10 highdSDS-d2o 40C, 1031.0, 2.83

1: W10 highdC12E5-d2o 40C, 1032.0, 2.83

